

OPTIMIZING SHARIA INTEGRATED MICRO-FINANCE INSTITUTIONS AS BUSINESS FINANCING SOLUTIONS TO ENHANCE THE ECONOMY AND WELFARE OF INDONESIA

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Abstract

Indonesian people is a society with high diverse culture and own a various commodities as well, both in goods and foods. In fact, by utilizing this diversity the Indonesian people are able to create promising business. However, Indonesia is not a country with a society that all have high information access to banking systems. Many Indonesians are afraid to deal with banks or they live in remote locations that can not be reached by banking system. That is where Integrated micro-finance take the important role. Integrated micro-finance becomes a concrete step for business financing in Indonesia, because it helps poor people to get out of poverty (according to the first point SDGs) by providing assistance other than money as well as training and business coaching to develop a good and sustainable business (in accordance with the eighth point SDGs). Integrated micro-finance can provide loans with requirements that are not as difficult as banking and spread well in the community (such as Bank Perkreditan Rakyat Syariah , Baitul Maal wa Tamwil and Koperasi). That is an important point because people from any levels of society can start a business for their livelihood. Using Sharia policy supports, it will make the consumers will feel safer due to unbound interest, because sometimes the interest becomes one thing that makes people fears of debt. In addition to the rising tide of "hijra" in Indonesia, Indonesia's level of confidence in all Sharia-related issues is increasing, becoming a great opportunity for Sharia integrated micro-finance to take advantage of this opportunity to attract markets and with the spirit of Indonesian people to own a business with good financing, I believe Sharia integrated micro finance will improve the Indonesian economy condition and consequently improve the welfare of the people of Indonesia.

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1. Introduction

Indonesia has been one of the first countries to develop commercial microfinance in Asia, with regulated financial institutions providing the bulk of microfinance services throughout the archipelago. Bank Rakyat Indonesia units have been in existence for twenty years, and some forms of 'People's credit banks' or BPRs, have appeared more than a century ago. Microcredit is defined by Bank Indonesia, the central bank, as a loan below Rp.50 million (US\$5,373), a financial product provided by formal and semi-formal financial providers in Indonesia. In addition to the success of commercial microfinance providers, Indonesia has also been a favourable ground for the development of numerous subsidised government programs, local and community-based financial institutions, cooperatives and NGOs.

Microfinance or microfinance has experienced very rapid development. Since the success of the Grameen Bank program introduced by Muhammad Yunus (2006 Nobel Peace Prize laureate) in Bangladesh in the early 1980s, world financial institutions have begun to pay greater attention to microfinance in an effort to alleviate poverty, and also make a profit.

Based on data published by the Microcredit Summit Campaign in 2012, a total of 1,746 microfinance programs were conducted and reached around 169 million clients in 2010 for the Asia-Pacific region only. This area is indeed the area that receives the most microfinance programs, in addition to the large population and also the high level of poor people. The level of program coverage provided by the Micro Finance Institution (MFI) reached 68.8 percent, in other words, from around 182.4 million poor people in the region, 125.53 million were granted access to microfinance programs.

In addition, Islamic Microfinance is a sector with great potential for growth. It is estimated that 72% of the population living in Muslim-majority countries do not use financial services, because they do not follow the teachings of Islam. Muslims use conventional financial products, but various surveys show that if they have a choice, they will use sharia compliance financial products. One objective of Islam is to support the most vulnerable, which is in accordance with the mission of microfinance. At present, Islamic microfinance is concentrated in three countries, one of which is Indonesia.

Although microfinance has been established 100 years ago and Islamic microfinance has begun to develop in Indonesia, the current financial service system has not been effective in empowering micro businesses and alleviating poverty. Though this business supports most (almost 95%) business entities in Indonesia and is believed to be an economic actor in a society that is resistant to national and international crisis turmoil. This paper aims to discuss how to optimize sharia microfinance in an integrated manner to support business financing so that it can be a solution to economic problems and welfare in Indonesia.

2. Literature Studies

Microfinance

Microfinance firstly defined as the provision of microloans to poor entrepreneurs and small businesses lacking access to banking and related services. The two main mechanisms for the delivery of financial services to such clients were:

1. Relationship-based banking for individual entrepreneurs and small businesses; and
2. Group-based models, where several entrepreneurs come together to apply for loans and other services as a group.

Over time, microfinance has emerged as a larger movement whose object is "a world in which as everyone, especially the poor and socially marginalized people and households have access to a wide range of affordable, high quality financial products and services, including not just credit but also savings, insurance, payment services, and fund transfers" (Christen, Rosenberg & Jayadeva, 2004).

Sharia Microfinance

Sharia microfinance differs from conventional microfinance in that it must adhere to the same principles as Islamic finance, which is structured to provide products for Muslim customers that are in compliance with the code of ethics and conduct laid out under sharia law. It utilizes a range of models to avoid elements forbidden under sharia, namely interest (riba) and uncertainty and deceit (gharar). Financial instruments are therefore designed to provide funds in a manner that avoids both interest payments while still taking into consideration the need to cover overhead and the cost of financing if the MFI is to be sustainable, and shares the risk of the investment between the financier and recipient or places it on the MFI alone.

Sharia microfinance’s exclusion of interest could alleviate a major criticism of conventional microfinance—namely the high interest rates charged on loans. Commonly available types of Sharia microfinance contracts that work in lieu of conventional loan agreements include:

- Cost plus markup (murabaha)
 - o Under the murabaha model, the MFI buys goods and resells them to the microentrepreneurs for the cost of the goods plus a markup to cover administrative costs. The borrower often pays for the goods in equal installments, and the microfinance institution owns the goods until the last installment is settled. The goods legally remain in the MFI’s possession until fully purchased, so the risk associated with the endeavor also remains with the MFI.
- Profit and loss sharing (musharaka and mudaraba)
 - o Musharaka is equity participation in a business venture where the MFI and the client share profits and losses according to a predetermined ratio.
 - o Mudaraba is a form of trustee financing with one party acting as the financier and the other providing managerial expertise and executing the project; profits are shared according to a predetermined ratio while losses are borne entirely by the MFI.

Table 1: Differences between Conventional and Islamic Microfinance

Category	Conventional Microfinance	Islamic Microfinance
Category of poor	One category	Two levels: 1. deeply poor who do not need loan but social safety net and charitable fund (<i>zakah</i>), 2. moderately poor who will be better of if they obtain credit for running microenterprises
Based of financing	Debt based and interest based approach	Profit and loss sharing (PLS) approach, free of interest (<i>riba</i>) and uncertainty (<i>gharar</i>)
Approach/target of empowerment	The poor and woman	The poorest and family
Sources of fund	External funds, saving of clients	External funds, saving of clients and Islamic charity fund.
Dealing with default	Group/centre pressure and threats	Group/centre/spouse guarantee, and Islamic ethics.
Social Development Program	Secular	Religious (behaviour, ethics and social

Source: Obaidullah (2008b: 11-12), Ahmed (2002: 41)

Microfinance Institutions

Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) are financial institutions that are specifically established to provide business development services and community empowerment, either through loans or financing in micro-scale business to members and the community, savings management, as well as providing business development consulting services that are not solely seeking profit. There are three types of microfinance institutions, namely:

- a. Formal institutions such as village banks and cooperatives
- b. Semi-formal institutions such as non-governmental organizations
- c. Informal sources such as money release.

The national policy of developing microfinance institutions has a vision that every household in every village and region throughout the archipelago in Indonesia has access to quality and sustainable financial services such as savings, time deposits, credit and various microfinance services needed. This is intended to create opportunities for poor families and low-income community groups to improve welfare by reducing life vulnerabilities, increasing business activities, creating jobs and increasing their income. For this reason, a comprehensive financial

system needs to be implemented in the medium and long term in order to expand the reach of financial services for poor families and low income groups.

Current Microfinance Condition

The number of business actors of microfinance institutions or MFIs continues to grow. Throughout 2017 there were an additional 51 MFIs registered with the Financial Services Authority. OJK noted that in 2017, there were 180 MFIs. Increased from 2016 as many as 129 MFIs. From the number of MFIs until the end of last year, 151 of them carried out conventional business. The details are 132 MFIs in the form of cooperatives, and the remaining 19 are limited liability companies. Meanwhile, there are 29 MFIs that conduct business according to sharia principles.

According to data from the Ministry of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises, the number of SMEs in the country reached 55.2 million, consisting of 54,559,969 micro enterprises. The Financial Services Authority (OJK) also noted that Indonesian banks in general have complied with the OJK rules that mandate them to allocate 10% of their loan portfolio to small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in 2016 which will be increased to 20% in 2018. The Indonesian government's support for SMEs continues to improve too as evidenced by an increase in the allocation of the People's Business Credit (KUR) or small business loans from 30 trillion IDR in 2015 to 120 trillion IDR in 2016. In addition, OJK's decision to allow multifinance companies to disburse KUR will enhance the people's access to small business loans. Such a strategy is in line with President Joko Widodo's efforts to bolster the SME segment through simplifying processes in relation to starting a company and obtaining licenses.

Microfinance development and microfinance institutions are growing so rapidly. from these developments there are two who steal attention:

1. BRI

BRI also participated in the Branchless Banking government program called BRILink. In 2012 the Government and Bank Indonesia had prepared Branchless Banking or banking services without relying on branch offices and using technology to reach its customers. Following up on this in 2015 the Financial Services Authority (OJK), which was the authority in the supervision of banks and financial institutions, then launched the LAKU PANDAI program (Officeless Financial Services in Inclusive Financial Framework) Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk then followed up on this service using the BRILink Program. This is certainly very beneficial for BRI because BRI has customers throughout Indonesia to remote areas of the country. With BRILink, BRI can reach its customers in remote areas, without having to build an office in the area. Now this individual who serves the BRILink business is called the BRILink Agent. Transactions that can be done at BRILink are: Refill phone balance, Payment of prepaid electricity, Payment Finance FIF, BAF, WOM and OTO, Deposit cash, Withdraw cash (Using an ATM card), etc.

2. BAZNAS

Microfinance BAZNAS is a productive financing assistance agency to mustahik with the principle of non for profit in the context of business development.

Capital is the main factor needed to develop a business unit. Lack of capital in small and medium enterprises due to the characteristics of closed businesses, relying on capital from the owner which is very limited in number, while loan capital from banks or other financial institutions is difficult to obtain because the administrative and technical requirements requested by the bank cannot be fulfilled.

The main objective is to provide access to productive financing services to mustahik in order to develop its business.

3. Discussion

Microfinance in Indonesia has been well developed and in line with MSMEs to develop since 1980. However, once the Sharia economy developed in Indonesia, including the Sharia economy supporting integrated microfinance to bias and help small communities in Indonesia.

However, limited information about Islamic economics, especially Sharia microfinance institutions in Indonesia, is still a barrier to the success of integrated Islamic microfinance institutions. So, one possible way is needed to be able to attract Indonesian people to start a business with the help of an integrated Sharia microfinance institution. A good way to use is to directly help the community with programs that also support the progress of its business. One of the programs is by going directly to a small community by training the community before giving funds to do business. After that it provides training and programs that support activities of small communities such as halal forums, providing digital financial services, and expanding access to markets and financial technology.

It is also necessary to collaborate with other parties, one of which is by empowering Islamic boarding schools as a community that can help this activity run. Because Islamic boarding schools are one place where Islamic economics can grow and develop, then by inviting Islamic boarding schools as agents of change through coaching and training activities on Islamic economics and establishing sharia LKM branches in Islamic boarding schools will encourage Islamic economic activities around the pesantren area. With these activities, it is expected that funds for MFIs can be used and provide benefits to businesses and create independence for borrowers.

The halal certification forum is important because Indonesia now occupies the position of the two global Muslim tourist destinations which are index travels in 2018 issued by the Crescent Rating Master Card and also become a standard for workers in Indonesia, one of which is halal certification for businesses that in countries such as food, accommodation and travel. Then, with the halal certification in a business, you can add the number of Muslim visitors who are dating the business. So, by providing a halal certification forum to help improve the quality of halal in Indonesia, also increase the number of administrators due to halal certification.

With the existence of digital financial services for the fostered institutions of Islamic financial institutions, it will be easier for consumers to make payments to these parties, it can also increase competitiveness to maintain the business. Then, expanding access to the ecomers market, assisted assisted merchants of Islamic microfinance institutions to improve products because of their wider market reach. This can be done using good and periodic training and monitoring. So, the function of microfinance institutions that are able to provide the right results and can be used by the community to the fullest. And Islamic microfinance institutions can be used in countries in Indonesia and become the main choice for Indonesian people to finance especially small and medium micro enterprises. Then, in addition to targeting small communities, we also encourage microfinance institutions to help and help millennials to do business. One way is to make changes for youth communities who have a passion for doing business and want to minimize risks in their business. So, we target the "Hijrah" communities that are mushrooming and growing rapidly in Indonesia and Sharia LKMs must also organize and conduct business development activities for young children organized by both the government and non-government.

By utilizing young people in Indonesia, Sharia microfinance institutions can grow through communication activities formed by millennials because millennials have a very wide network of communication, information and technology. And that can encourage micro-Sharia institutions to become bigger. Sharia microfinance institutions in providing services to millennials must provide training and training, and develop the same products as those given to entrepreneurs in the MFI. Like halal certification forums, digital financial services, and accessibility are also in great demand by millennials who want to do business. because by being used that is coupled with the Shariah-compliant concept, it will stimulate the community to conduct business activities through Islamic microfinance institutions which are believed to be the right one choice because they have a good program and their activities are in accordance with what is stated by Islam.

Therefore, we believe financial institutions that make it possible to be a solution for financing with the record of having coaching, training, and products that can benefit the community and have good supervision for their customers.

4. Conclusion

Through this paper, it is hoped that the Sharia micro-institution can develop and benefit the community with a note that it must have breakthrough programs that are close to the community and have good and clearly monitored business development, training and business development. Sharia micro-institutions can also develop with the note that they must be close to the community, such as taking part in coaching and training on businesses / businesses for small traders, small communities, or millennials. close to the community and understand the needs of the community. It is expected that this integrated Islamic microfinance institution will be a solution for people in Indonesia to be able to have a much better livelihood and have a business that can survive and produce so that the community becomes independent with its own business and has financing in accordance with Sharia which gives a sense of security especially to the Muslims so not afraid and worried about the problem of financing which is sure to avoid riba’.

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